

EMPLOYMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE GRADUATES IN KAZAKHSTAN

Ainur Bazarbayeva⁹

Abstract

One of the big problems for computer science graduates is employability and adaptation in the new workplace. Nowadays, many factors are crucial in transitioning from university to a job. This quantitative study aimed to determine how graduates search for jobs and the most frequently faced problem. Therefore, one hundred twenty graduate computer science students from various higher education institutions in Kazakhstan completed a questionnaire for this qualitative study. Findings show that for job searching, graduates use internet platforms more than other instruments, and the most prevalent problem among them is a lack of experience and qualification. The results can enhance training programs and methodologies for improved readiness for the post-graduation labour market.

Keywords

Computer science, graduates, job finding, employment, career challenges, graduate surveys

1 Introduction

Youth unemployment is among the most common problems in many continents and countries. It is a social situation resulting from economic dislocations or redundancy, now studied sociologically as a product of work institutions, governmental policies, and cultural interpretations (Boland et al., 2023).

Most employers try to hire candidates with hard and soft skills, such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills. These skills are one factor that impact graduates' employability after HEIs (Kyureghyan & Khusainova, 2022; Sahudin, 2022). There is a gap between employers' expectations and graduates' skills after HEIs, so this situation highlights the importance of upgrading the curriculum (Wahab et al., 2024).

Moreover, skills like critical thinking and lifelong learning, adaptability in changing situations in the labour market, and self-management are essential for having a good beginning in the career way (Troškova & Katane, 2024; Lan, 2022). Graduates with a combination of these skills will essentially have employability chances and effectiveness during challenges at the workplace (Wahab et al., 2024; Lan, 2022). Ideas like involving stakeholders in curriculum designing and educational processes allow students to have experience; after that follows self-reflection and peer learning, which are very important for developing socio-emotional skills ("Employer input to curriculum and assessment", 2023). 2023).

Furthermore, utilizing serious games during the learning process follows visible improvement skills like critical thinking and teamwork, which are vital for employability (Yanes et al., 2023). Seminars for graduates organised in collaboration with employers demonstrated an effective impact on employability metrics and securing job offers based on mock interviews (O'Regan et al., 2022). Also, creating career centres that escort students and

⁹ Kazakh National Women's Teacher Training University, Almaty, Gogol, 114 k1, 050000, Kazakhstan.email. aynur555a@gmail.com

have connections with the industry ensures filling gaps between industry and HEI (Sysoeva et al., 2023). All these actions are vital for preparing students for future job competition and meeting employers' expectations (Andersson & Clausen, 2024).

2 Literature review

The education system dramatically impacts students' employability after graduation by forming professional skills and competencies in appropriate fields. Research results in Tanzania show that some curriculum reforms increase employability chances by making education relevant and responsive to the job market (Koboli et al., 2024). Southeastern European experience highlights the necessity for tailored approaches and individual work for university-job transition, and it had an impact on increasing youth employability (Bojadjeva et al., 2022; Surya, 2022). The Indian National Education Policy 2020 aimed to fill gaps in skills between HEIs offered and employers expected to accentuate the importance of equipping students with essential skills for future careers (Sharma & Trivedi, 2023). Thus, comprehensive reforms that involve integrated curriculum updates, labour market matching, and institutional support are essential to improving youth employability.

Youth unemployment and complicated or long job searching are complex issues influenced by various factors. Key reasons are listed below:

a) Skills mismatch. There is often a remarkable gap between the qualifications graduates acquire through education and the skills employers need. This mismatching is one of the main troubles during employment, whereas many graduates have limited critical competencies for available jobs in the market, particularly in digital and technical fields (World Economic Forum, 2024);

b) Economic conditions. Weak macroeconomics can strongly impact youth employment, and economic decreases impact fewer job opportunities in the job market, making it harder for graduates to find employment (Görlich et al., 2013; Feng et al., 2023);

c) Experience requirements. Employers often prefer candidates with backgrounds, leaving young job seekers disadvantaged. This preference for experienced workers can lead to youth unemployment rates (House of Lords Library, 2023);

d) Career ambitions. Young professionals select jobs they pursue and often wait for vacancies appropriate to their goals and visions rather than accepting available places. This tendency can follow lengthy periods of unemployment (Sikora, 2010);

e) Geographical disparities. Youth unemployment depends on the region, and in some regions, it is due to local economic conditions, industry presence, and educational opportunities. Regions with bounded economic development often have a higher youth unemployment value (World Economic Forum, 2024).

Addressing these issues requires coordinated efforts from policymakers, educators, and employers to ensure that young people are adequately prepared for the labor market and have access to quality job opportunities.

Several studies have paid special attention to social connections in the job search process, probably due to the many job seekers who find work using this method. A study by Franzen and Hangartner (2006) found that the share of employment through social networks ranged from 83% in the Philippines to 26% in Finland and Austria. Almost 44% of respondents in the United States also noted that they found a job through social contacts. Structural approaches (Lin, 2008) and behavioral approaches are used in this field (Wolff & Moser, 2009).

In this study, three research questions based on a literature review followed below:

RQ1: What are the most popular ways to find jobs among computer science graduates in Kazakhstan?

RQ2: What are the most prevalent problems among computer science graduates in Kazakhstan when searching for jobs?

RQ3: What help do computer science graduates from higher education institutions want to better prepare for employment and the job market?

3 Methodology

This qualitative study included a questionnaire among one hundred twenty CS graduate students from different higher education institutions in Kazakhstan. This quantitative study aimed to determine how graduates search for jobs and the most frequently faced problem. The results can help improve training programs and methods for better preparation for the labour market after graduation. Also, the steps of this research provided by the author can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Steps of the research study

Source: own work

Tool

Two discussions with different groups of colleagues helped the researchers guarantee the questionnaire's validity. During the discussion, colleagues in this field discussed the questionnaire questions to improve them. The experts' recommendations were applied to change the questions' wording and order. After the initial fix, a secondary discussion took place with another group of experts, after which there were only minor changes, after which the researchers began a pilot study. A pilot study was conducted on 13 respondents, after which the researchers saw preliminary data that were applied for further analysis. After conducting the pilot study, we also requested feedback from the respondents. Thus, their feedback helped improve the questions' working and order. The Ethics Committee of the Kazakh National Women's Teacher Training University approved the research protocols prior to the start of the study.

Data collection and analysis

The questionnaire was created using Google Forms and was sent by social media to some higher education institutions in different regions of Kazakhstan. Data collection took about one month, and Jamovi statistical software was used to analyze the collected data.

Limitation

Despite the valuable information this study provides about graduates' employability problems, it is important to indicate its limitations. Because of the limited sample size, there is a potential for response bias. Therefore, a more in-depth study requires a more representative

sample, which may give slightly different results. Students' answers in this research may not accurately represent the students' real experience because not all graduate students actively searched for jobs. Also, conducting a qualitative or mixed method study may have provided more detailed information, but these steps can be carried out in the future. Moreover, the results may not be usable to all due to the difference in culture, language, or economic conditions.

4 Results and discussion

A descriptive analysis was conducted to understand the number of respondents by gender, region, and type of HEI. 96 (80%) of the respondents were female, and only 48 (40%) of all respondents studied at a national HEI. Regarding the regional characteristics of the respondents, the majority, 83 (69.1%), are from Almaty city, while others are from Zhetysu, Aktobe, Almaty, and other regions.

Tab. 1: Descriptive statistics of the respondents

Gender	Number (%), n=120	Type of HEI	Number (%), n=120	Location	Number (%), n=120
Male	24 (20)	National HEI	48 (40)	Almaty city	83 (69,1)
Female	96 (80)	University	72 (60)	Zhetysu region	15 (12,5)
				Aktobe region	8 (6,67)
				Almaty region	6 (5)
				others	8 (6,67)

Source: own work

RQ 1: Figure 2 represents the respondents' answers and clearly shows that the most popular way for 73 (60.83%) CS graduates to find jobs is through *internet platforms*. After that, graduates use *professional social networks and communities* 36 (30%) and *recommendations from acquaintances or friends* 35 (29.16%) with little difference. Consequently, graduates use *company job vacancy mailing lists* 20 (16.67%) and *job fairs and career events* 15 (12.5%) less frequently than other job-finding methods.

Fig. 2: Preferred job search methods among computer science graduates

Source: own work

The binomial test can be used to determine whether the frequency distribution of a sample is the same as that of the population. It is used to determine whether the frequency distribution of a variable with only two values in the sample corresponds.

In our cases, the binomial test has two hypotheses. The first is the null hypothesis, which states that the sample's frequency distribution corresponds to that of the population. The alternative hypothesis is that the sample's frequency distribution does not correspond to the population's.

As shown in Table 2, the p-value is below the significance level of 5%, and the result is therefore significant. Consequently, the null hypothesis must be rejected. In terms of content, this means that the preferred job search methods ratio of the graduates in CS specialisation (=sample) does not differ significantly from that of all CS graduates in HEIs (=population).

Tab. 2: Binomial test of preferred job search methods

	Level	Count	Total	Proportion	p
Internet platforms	yes	73	120	0.608	0.022
	no	47	120	0.392	0.022
Recommendations from acquaintances or friends	yes	35	120	0.292	< .001
	no	85	120	0.708	< .001
Company job vacancy mailing lists	yes	20	120	0.167	< .001
	no	100	120	0.833	< .001
Job fairs and carrier meeting	yes	15	120	0.125	< .001
	no	105	120	0.875	< .001
Professional social networks and communities	yes	36	120	0.300	< .001
	no	84	120	0.700	< .001

Source: own work

RQ 2: In response to the second question, 72 (60%) respondents reported that their lack of experience and qualification is their most common problem. Fewer respondents answered that they have other problems, such as *unsatisfactory job conditions* 16 (13.33%), *mismatching with the requirements of the employer* 12 (10%), and *challenges during the interview* 10 (8.33%). However, 24 (20%) respondents answered that they had other problems but did not want to say the type of the problems.

Fig. 3: Key job search difficulties among computer science graduates

Source: own work

Here, we conducted a binomial test with the same hypotheses and results shown in Table 3. The p-value is below the significance level, and the result is significant for all points. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and can state that the job search difficulties ratio among CS graduates does not differ significantly from that of all CS graduates in HEIs.

Tab. 3: *Binomial test of job search difficulties among computer science graduates*

	Level	Count	Total	Proportion	p
Lack of experience and qualification	yes	72	120	0.600	0.035
	no	48	120	0.400	0.035
Challenges during the interview	yes	10	120	0.083	< .001
	no	110	120	0.917	< .001
Unsatisfactory job conditions	yes	16	120	0.133	< .001
	no	104	120	0.867	< .001
Mismatching with the requirements of the employer	yes	12	120	0.100	< .001
	no	108	120	0.900	< .001

Source: own work

RQ 3: Regarding the third question, the researcher asked CS graduates about support and help they wait for from HEIs, and the results are shown in Figure 4. Most expected help, such as *internship opportunities* and *organising career fairs and employer events*, with the same indicator 39 (32.5%). In addition, support like *career counseling* 11 (9.17%) and *updated training programs* 12 (10%) were less expected types of help.

For this part of the research data, the binomial test was conducted with the hypotheses above, and the results are presented in Table 4. The p-value below shows the relevant result, and the null hypothesis was rejected. Consequently, the preferred help and support ratio among CS graduates does not differ significantly from that of all CS graduates in HEIs.

Fig. 4: *Help and support that CS graduates want from universities for further employment*

Source: own work

Tab. 4: Binomial test of help and support that CS graduates want from HEIs

	Level	Count	Total	Proportion	p
Carrier fairs and employer events	yes	38	120	0.317	<.001
	no	82	120	0.683	<.001
Interview and resume workshops	yes	23	120	0.192	<.001
	no	97	120	0.808	<.001
Startup and business support	yes	16	120	0.133	<.001
	no	104	120	0.867	<.001
Update training programs	yes	12	120	0.100	<.001
	no	108	120	0.900	<.001
Internships	yes	38	120	0.317	<.001
	no	82	120	0.683	<.001
Career counselling	yes	11	120	0.092	<.001
	no	109	120	0.908	<.001
Soft skills development workshops	yes	16	120	0.133	<.001
	no	104	120	0.867	<.001
Professional networking support	yes	17	120	0.142	<.001
	no	103	120	0.858	<.001

Source: own work

A Chi-square statistical test was used to determine whether a difference between observed and expected data is due to chance or a relationship between the variables. There is a significant association between gender and preferred job-searching methods, particularly internet platforms ($\chi^2 = 4.23$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.040$). Also, the test shows an association between categorical variables such as gender and preferred support from the HEIs (internships) ($\chi^2 = 4.66$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.031$). It proves that male and female graduates prefer to look for work through online platforms to varying degrees, and they also prefer internships from universities to varying degrees.

5 Discussion

People's sources of information in their job search can be divided into informal (e.g., friends, family, and acquaintances) and formal (e.g., online job ads). Although informal and formal sources are important for job seekers, informal sources can provide several benefits, including job search tips and insider information about vacancies (Wanberg & Csillag, 2020).

The first research question revealed that graduates are more likely to prefer internet platforms and professional social networks, which is appropriate in our digital age. Professional social networks and communities are also slightly less popular, which also helps people find jobs or employees. At the same time, unlike online platforms, you can read and share useful

professional information, blogs, and posts here. Regarding job fairs and career events, they are currently organized by HEIs for their graduates and students, but in other places, they are not as popular as before.

Researchers van Hooft, Wanberg and Van Hoyer say that for the job search process to be of high quality, it must include four important components. First, the applicant must have clear goals and follow these goals. Secondly, the applicant must apply a focused research strategy and various methods, including informal sources, and plan time and resources. Thirdly, the applicant must control attention, emotions, and motivation. Also, the search process should include reflection on progress and lessons from failures for achievement (van Hooft et al., 2013).

Other studies have shown that graduates who planned, monitored progress and evaluated their performance in the interview reported a higher intensity of job search (Chawla et al., 2019; da Motta Veiga & Gabriel, 2016); they sent more summaries and received more invitations to interview (Turban et al., 2009).

Many studies show a significant correlation between a lack of work experience and employability rates among fresh graduates. This reason often makes the employability process more complex and longer; also, there is a problem with having this experience (Hewitt & Grenfell, 2022; Helyer & Lee, 2014).

Furthermore, research directed at unemployed MBA graduates shows that one of the most important elements for successful career starting is appropriate curriculum adaptation to industry needs, potentially increasing employability (Singh et al., 2024). Overall, appropriate professional experience and qualifications are essential to the employability of recent graduates.

Moreover, fostering students' self-sufficiency through active community-oriented learning allows graduates to manage their careers and decide their futures (Wise, 2021). This systematic strategy has advantages, such as preparing students for a relevant and lifelong activity in the workforce and raising their employability chances (Bridgstock & Jackson, 2019).

6 Conclusion

This quantitative study shows that internet platforms and professional social networks are the most popular tools for job searching among CS graduates in Kazakhstan HEIs. After that, graduates also face difficulties during the employment process, and one of the most significant troubles is a lack of experience in appropriate fields. There are also other difficulties, but more graduates with significant differences mentioned this problem. Regarding the question about help and support from HEIs, around 40% of respondents would prefer more internships and career events to fill the skills and qualification gap and improve employability. The binomial test was also performed to check whether the sample's frequency distribution coincides with the distribution in the general sample of CS graduates, and a chi-square test to see if a categorical variable fits the hypothetical distribution, such as gender and other indicators.

Therefore, future research should focus on a deeper study of graduate employment and exploring partnerships between industry and higher education institutions to develop a curriculum involving industry in the educational process. A qualitative approach would provide more detailed and in-depth information about the situation on the labour market, graduates, and partnerships between universities and industries.

7 Resources

- Amalia, L., Kuregyan., Mariya, A., Khusainova. (2022). 2. Soft skills as key competences for successful employability of graduate students. *Vestnik Samarskogo gosudarstvennogo tehničeskogo universiteta*, doi: 10.17673/vsgtu-pps.2022.4.9
- Anne, Hewitt., Laura, Grenfell. (2022). 1. A call for regulatory reform to make work experience accessible rather than an obstacle. *Alternative Law Journal*, doi: 10.1177/1037969x221123602
- Chawla, N., Gabriel, A. S., da Motta Veiga, S. P., & Slaughter, J. E. (2019). Does feedback matter for job search self-regulation? It depends on feedback quality. *Personnel Psychology*, 72(4), 513-541.
- Daniela, Mamucevska, Bojadjieva., Marijana, Cvetanoska., Kristijan, Kozheski., Alen, Mujčinović., Slaven, Gašparović. (2022). 2. The Impact of Education on Youth Employability: The Case of Selected Southeastern European Countries. *Youth & Society*, doi: 10.1177/0044118X211069403
- da Motta Veiga, S. P., & Gabriel, A. S. (2016). The role of self-determined motivation in job search: A dynamic approach. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 101(3), 350.
- Evgeniya, A., Sysoeva., Viktoriya, Zhukova., Lidiya, V., Shirokova. (2023). 5. Aspects of implementation of models of interaction between career centers of universities and industrial enterprises in the conditions of labor market transformation. *Ėkonomika v promyšlennosti*, doi: 10.17073/2072-1633-2023-2-238-246
- Feng, S., Lu, J., Terada-Hagiwara, A., & Qi, W. (2023). A Closer Look at Causes of Youth Unemployment in the People's Republic of China. *ADB Briefs*.
- Franzen, A., & Hangartner, D. (2006). Social networks and labour market outcomes: The non-monetary benefits of social capital. *European sociological review*, 22(4), 353-368.
- G., M., Koboli., Coletha, C., Ngirwa., Patrick, Manyengo. (2024). 1. Managing Employability Challenges among Graduates: The Role of Curricula Reforms. doi: 10.9734/arjass/2024/v22i8566
- Görllich, D., Stepanok, I., & Al-Hussami, F. (2013). Youth unemployment in Europe and the world: Causes, consequences and solutions.
- Hanna, Chornoivan. (2023). 1. Development of Employment Skills and Career Growth of Higher Education Graduates in the Context of Best International Practices. *Problemi osviti*, doi: 10.52256/2710-3986.2-99.2023.07
- House of Lords Library. (2023, September 28). *Causes of youth unemployment: Lords committee report*. <https://lordslibrary.parliament.uk/causes-of-youth-unemployment-lords-committee-report/>
- Joanna, Sikora. (2010). Returns to ambition: The role of early career plans in the transition from education to work.

-
- Lin, N. (2008). A network theory of social capital. *The handbook of social capital*, 50(1), 69.
- Mai, Thi, Quynh, Lan. (2022). 4. Competencies Contributing to Graduates Employability. *VNU Journal of Science: Education Research*, doi: 10.25073/2588-1159/vnuer.4642
- Marina, Troškova., Irēna, Katane. (2024). 3. Employability of prospective specialists as a set of internal resources and readiness to ensure their own employment in changing labour market conditions. *Education. Innovation. Diversity*, doi: 10.17770/eid2024.1.7777
- Md., Hasan, Shimum, Wahab., Mosharrof, Hosen., Md, Asadul, Islam., Mohammad, Abdul, Matin, Chowdhury., Amer, Hamzah, Jantan., Sazali, Abdul, Wahab. (2024). 1. Graduate employability: A bibliometric analysis. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, doi: 10.1002/joe.22267
- Miriam, O'Regan., Aiden, Carthy., Colm, McGuinness., Philip, Owende. (2022). 3. Employer collaboration in developing graduate employability: a pilot study in Ireland. *Journal of education and training*, doi: 10.1108/et-03-2022-0081
- Nacim, Yanes., Ikram, Bououd., Leila, Jamel., Nazik, M., Alturki. (2023). 2. Serious gaming for graduates employability enhancement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1324397
- Nathan, Wise. (2021). 5. Workforce Preparation and Employability. doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-0247-4_15
- O'Brien, G., & Siggers, D. (2023). Employer input to curriculum and assessment. *How to Enable the Employability of University Graduates*, 79–88. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781803926513.00021>
- Ruth, Bridgstock., Denise, Jackson. (2019). 4. Strategic institutional approaches to graduate employability: navigating meanings, measurements and what really matters. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, doi: 10.1080/1360080X.2019.1646378
- Ruth, Helyer., Dionne, Lee. (2014). 2. The Role of Work Experience in the Future Employability of Higher Education Graduates. *Higher Education Quarterly*, doi: 10.1111/HEQU.12055
- Shuib, Sahudin. (2022). 5. Literature Review on the Factors Affecting Employability of Engineering Graduates. *Asian journal of engineering education*, doi: 10.11113/ajee2022.6n1.75
- Sonia, Sharma., Neetika, Trivedi. (2023). 4. Employability & Youth - A Perspective in Harmony with NEP 2020. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, doi: 10.36948/ijfmr.2023.v05i06.8806
- Tom, Boland., Ray, Griffin. (2023). 1. Unemployment. *The Blackwell Encyclopedia of Sociology*, doi: 10.1002/9781405165518.wbeosu002.pub2
- Turban, D. B., Stevens, C. K., & Lee, F. K. (2009). EFFECTS OF CONSCIENTIOUSNESS AND EXTRAVERSION ON NEW LABOR MARKET ENTRANTS' JOB SEARCH:

THE MEDIATING ROLE OF METACOGNITIVE ACTIVITIES AND POSITIVE EMOTIONS. *Personnel Psychology*, 62(3), 553-573.

- Van Hooft, E. A., Wanberg, C. R., & Van Hoye, G. (2013). Moving beyond job search quantity: Towards a conceptualization and self-regulatory framework of job search quality. *Organizational Psychology Review*, 3(1), 3-40.
- Velappa, Jayaraman, Surya. (2022). 3. The Impact of Education on Youth Employability: The Case of Selected Southeastern European Countries. *Youth & Society*, doi: 10.1177/0044118x211069403
- Vibeke, Andersson., Helene, Balslev, Clausen. (2024). 1. *Building Employability Skills for Graduate Students*. doi: 10.54337/nlc.v14i1.8051
- Wanberg, C.R., Ali, A.A., & Csillag, B. (2020). Job Seeking: The Process and Experience of Looking for a Job. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*.
- Wolff, H. G., & Moser, K. (2009). Effects of networking on career success: a longitudinal study. *Journal of applied psychology*, 94(1), 196.
- World Economic Forum. (2024, August). *Global youth employment: Future jobs*. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2024/08/global-youth-employment-future-jobs/>
- Youth Employment UK. (n.d.). *Youth unemployment*. Retrieved November 7, 2024, from <https://www.youthemployment.org.uk/youth-unemployment/>